

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values in acetone solution ($8-12 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. The μ_{eff} values (1.86–1.99 B.M.) of the Cu^{2+} complexes correspond to the presence of the one unpaired electron. However no specific information regarding their stereochemistry² could be drawn from the magnetic moment data.

Electronic spectral bands at 15 385 and 18 870 cm^{-1} are observed in the spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition respectively, indicating³ square planar environment around Cu^{2+} . A single broad band centering around $\sim 15\,155 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed in the other Cu^{2+} complexes, indicating⁴ distorted octahedral geometries. From the ir spectra conductance and analysis we conclude that all the Cd^{2+} complexes are hexa-coordinated except the complex with nicotinic acid which is tetrahedral.

In nicotinic acid complexes the carboxyl vibration remains unchanged thus excluding the possibility of metal to oxygen coordination. However the pyridine part of the molecules exhibits appreciable shift. Bands around 1 580 and 1 550 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ modes, and pyridine ring vibration around 1 000, 990, 600 and 410 cm^{-1} indicate that coordination of the ligand takes place via pyridine ring nitrogen⁵. So the nicotinic acid acts and coordinates as monodentate ligand in the Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complexes.

Infrared spectra of the nicotinamide and isonicotinamide complexes do not show any appreciable shift in the $\nu_{C=O}$ band but show considerable negative shifts (50–75 cm^{-1}) in case of ν_{NH} (asymmetric and symmetric) bands. The δ_{NH_2} mode of the ligands (1 605–1 615 cm^{-1}) reduced in intensity and shifted towards higher frequency side (1 620–1 640 cm^{-1}). However positive shift of pyridine ring vibration (10–15 cm^{-1}) are observed in the ir spectra of the complexes.

The significant shifts of the pyridine ring vibrations, ν_{NH} and δ_{NH_2} bands due to bonding of the nitrogen atoms clearly indicate⁶ the bidentate nature of the nicotinamide and isonicotinamide.

In 2-benzoylpyridine and 3-benzoylpyridine complexes, the ir spectra indicate a positive shift of pyridine ring vibration indicating the coordination through pyridine nitrogen to the ligands. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band of the ligands occurring at 1 680–1 670 cm^{-1} shifted to 1 650–1 640 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating⁷ coordination of carbonyl oxygen of the ligands to the metal ions. The non-ligand bands occurring at 520–510, 445–440 and 300–268 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to ν_{M-O} , ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O_2} modes respectively⁸.

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Characterisation and X-Ray Diffraction Studies on $M(\text{bipyridyl})_2(\text{MoO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ Complexes with Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

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Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 4 October 1988, accepted 22 February 1989

THE paper reports the structural study on the complexes of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2,2'-bipyridyl formed in presence of MoO_4^{2-} oxoanion. Unit cell parameters have been calculated on the basis of X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complexes.

Experimental

A mixture of powdered $\text{MMoO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Ni}/\text{Co}$) mixed with an aqueous solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl in 1 : 2 molar ratio was digested on a water-bath for 6–7 h. The solid material dissolved gradually to yield a clear solution which was evaporated till crystals (pink in case of Ni^{2+} , and orange in case of Co^{2+}) separated out. The crystals were filtered, washed 3–4 times with ethanol–water (80 : 20), recrystallised from water and dried (P_4O_{10}): Elemental analysis data : Ni^{2+} complex (Found : Ni, 9.98; N, 10.21; Mo, 17.0. $\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{MoO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires : N 10.20; Ni, 10.56; Mo, 17.48%). Co^{2+} complex (Found : Co, 10.01; N, 9.68; Mo,

TABLE 1 - POWDER DIFFRACTION DATA

Scanning rate = 1°(2θ)/cm, Chart speed = 2 cm min⁻¹

Peak No.	2θ	Relative intensity I/I ₀ × 100	sin ² θ	hkl
(i) Ni(bipy) ₂ MoO ₄ ·H ₂ O.				
1	10.31	6.17	0.007 9	0.007 9 (110)
2	11.96	11.55	0.010 8	0.010 8 (002)
3	13.58	100.00	0.013 9	0.014 8 (102)
4	15.22	88.58	0.017 5	0.018 7 (112)
5	16.94	25.99	0.021 7	0.025 5 (211)
6	17.57	24.67	0.023 3	0.024 4 (003)
7	20.37	89.82	0.031 7	0.033 7 (220)
8	20.48	94.84	0.031 6	0.032 3 (113)
9	22.36	21.53	0.037 5	0.038 3 (301)
10	23.92	79.01	0.042 9	0.042 5 (222)
11	24.63	24.03	0.045 5	0.046 5 (302)
12	27.39	7.18	0.056 0	0.056 1 (223)
13	30.65	7.18	0.069 8	0.070 08 (411)
14	31.47	13.40	0.073 5	0.074 0 (331)
15	33.99	27.34	0.084 3	0.083 6 (205)
16	36.46	19.18	0.097 8	0.097 6 (006)
17	39.14	5.85	0.112 2	0.113 8 (512)
				0.113 5 (206)
18	41.54	8.65	0.125 7	0.125 7 (522)
19	43.92	12.92	0.139 8	0.140 8 (117)
20	45.22	7.18	0.147 8	0.147 0 (425)
21	49.41	6.50	0.174 7	0.173 6 (008)
22	51.40	5.85	0.188 0	0.189 4 (208)
				0.189 1 (632)
23	55.06	4.37	0.213 6	0.213 2 (318)
24	59.09	4.65	0.243 1	0.241 5 (714)
				0.244 2 (616)

A = 0.003 963, a = 12.265 636 Å, C = 0.002 712 5,
 c = 14.825 773 Å, Cell volume = 2 230.475 5 Å³
 Density: Found, 1.858 2 (Calcd., 1.918 2 g cm⁻³)

(ii) Co(bipy)₂MoO₄·2H₂O.

1	10.71	22.76	0.008 717	0.008 717 (110)
2	11.62	100.00	0.010 25	0.011 2 (111)
3	13.94	59.39	0.014 7	0.014 6 (102)
4	14.59	34.17	0.016 1	0.017 4 (200)
5	17.05	23.64	0.021 9	0.021 7 (210)
6	17.33	20.21	0.022 7	0.023 0 (003)
7	18.11	18.17	0.024 7	0.024 3 (211)
8	18.88	17.04	0.026 9	0.027 3 (103)
9	19.85	28.31	0.029 7	0.031 7 (113)
10	21.48	66.67	0.034 7	0.034 8 (220)
11	22.22	41.24	0.037 7	0.037 3 (221)
12	23.67	43.63	0.042 0	0.041 7 (301)
13	23.99	40.07	0.043 1	0.043 5 (310)
14	25.14	25.46	0.047 3	0.049 7 (114)
15	26.96	19.39	0.054 3	0.053 8 (312)
16	28.15	8.62	0.059 1	0.059 2 (321)
17	31.84	12.80	0.075 0	0.074 0 (410)
18	32.75	8.62	0.079 4	0.079 6 (323)
19	37.73	15.56	0.104 5	0.103 2 (305)

A = 0.004 358, a = 11.695 893 Å, C = 0.002 560 0,
 c = 15.260 967 Å, Cell volume = 2 087 607 3 Å³
 Density: Found, 1.815 5 (Calcd., 1.805 0 g cm⁻³)

16.91, Co(bipy)₂(MoO₄)·2H₂O requires: Co, 10.39; N, 8.86; Mo, 16.91%.

Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The room temperature

magnetic moments of the complexes were determined by Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard. The X-ray data were recorded on a diffractometer using CuK_α 1.5443 Å radiation. The unit cell calculation was done for the tetragonal symmetry of the nickel and cobalt complexes. The cell parameters were calculated by the following equations¹⁻⁴; for tetragonal system, sin² θ (hkl) = A(h² + k²) + Cl² where, A = λ²/4a² and C = λ²/4C².

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance (in water) of the complexes (for nickel complex 93.45 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, for Co complexes 97.65 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) suggested the following solvolysis equilibrium⁵,

where, M = Ni/Co, on dissolution of the complexes. The effective magnetic moment of the nickel complex (2.97 B M) corresponds to octahedral Ni^{II} complexes. In electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit bands at 12 820 and 19 342 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to ³A_{1g} → ³T_{2g} and ³A_{1g} → ³T_{1g} (P) transitions. There is also a weak band at 14 947 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to spin-forbidden transition¹¹⁻¹³. The observed magnetic moment of the Co^{II} complex (1.95 B M) is in good agreement with reported value of Co^{II} spin paired complexes in octahedral field⁶⁻¹⁰. The Co^{II} complex shows an absorption band at 20 703 cm⁻¹ (as shoulder).

The Ni and Co complexes showed broad ir bands at 3 20-3 400 cm⁻¹ and medium intensity bands at 1 680 cm⁻¹ due to OH stretching and bending vibration respectively of coordinated water^{14,15}. The absorption for molybdate ion in these complexes lies at 800-1 000 cm⁻¹¹⁶. The ν₃ band appeared at 900 cm⁻¹ (medium) in the nickel complex and at 890 cm⁻¹ in the cobalt complex (very sharp). In the nickel and cobalt complexes the ν₃ band splits into two bands at 830 (sharp), 804 (weak) cm⁻¹, and at 850 (weak), 808 (medium) respectively. The splitting of ν₃ band suggest that the oxo-anion is bonded to the central metal in the solid state^{17,18}.

From X-ray powder diffraction data (Table 1) the experimental values of sin² θ are found to be in good agreement with the calculated values for tetragonal cells.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar for facilities, and to the Directors of R.S.I.C, Nagpur for X-ray analysis and C.D R.I., Lucknow for elemental analysis. Thanks are also due to Mr. A. B. Khare of this Department for helpful discussion.

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Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes with Bifunctional Tridentate Schiff Bases and Neutral Monodentate Ligands

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Manuscript received 10 May 1988, revised 3 February 1989, accepted 9 March 1989

In continuation of our work¹ on studies of Schiff base compounds of transition metals, we report here the effect of different monodentate ligands upon the mode of coordination of bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases, thiosemicarbazones of salicylaldehyde (saltsc), benzoin (benzts) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (naptsc) with Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes¹: To a weighed amount of NiCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O or MnCl₂·4H₂O was added salicylaldehyde/benzoin/2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in 1:1 molar ratio in ethanolic medium and stirred for 5–10 min in a magnetic stirrer. To it was added pyridine (py), γ -picoline (γ -pic), isoquinoline (iq) or hot ethanolic solution of thiourea (tu) in excess with constant stirring. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, conductance, magnetic, electronic and ir spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The conductance (in nitrobenzene) data (0.31–3.4 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{mol}^{-1}$) show that the compounds are non-electrolytes. The molecular weight measurement indicates that the compounds are monomeric.

The infrared spectra (nujol) of the Schiff bases show a broad and strong band at 3 200–2 800 cm^{-1} attributable to ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} modes. It disappears in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the deprotonation of the ligands. The ν_{C-N} band of the Schiff bases appearing at 1 600 $\pm$ 5 cm^{-1} shifted to 1 620–1 630 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating their coordination through azomethine nitrogen. Bands due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=S}$ modes of the Schiff bases were observed at 1 680 and 1 020 cm^{-1} , respectively. These bands disappear in the complexes indicating the thioenolisation of these ligands and their chelation through thiolic sulphur. This is further supported by appearance of bands at $\sim$ 1 380 (C–O) and $\sim$ 661 cm^{-1} (C–S). Thus the Schiff bases behave as bifunctional tridentate (O, N, S) ligands². The presence of coordinated nitrogen donor ligands, viz. pyridine, γ -picoline and isoquinoline, in the complexes were known from their $\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{C-N}$ bands found at 1 530–1 540 cm^{-1} , although the other band at $\sim$ 1 620 cm^{-1} was masked by the Schiff base band. In the compounds containing thiourea, the ν_{C-S} band of free thiourea shifted to lower frequency at 710–720 cm^{-1} indicating its coordination through the sulphur atom. Further the bands of the compounds observed in the far-infrared region at 420–440 and 610–625 cm^{-1} may be due to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} modes, respectively³.

The μ_{eff} values (3.7–4.1 B.M.) of the three blue Ni²⁺ complexes (sl. nos. 1, 2 and 3; Table 1) and absorption band at 14 925–15 873 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ transition suggest tetrahedral geometry for these complexes. The two brown complexes (sl. nos. 4 and 5; Table 1) showed bands at 11 904–12 121, 16 129–16 806 and 27 777–28 985 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, which